

Interaction of Sulphur Dichloride with Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene Group. Part II.

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During previous investigations with sulphur dichloride, it was observed that it reacts with substances containing the reactive methylene group, giving rise to products containing the grouping $-SCl$ (Naik and Jadhav, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 260).

When sulphur dichloride was made to react with the substances, enumerated in the table at the end, under the same conditions as used by Naik and Jadhav, a gummy mass was obtained which was very difficult to work up. When attempts were made to purify these products by repeated purifications in mixed solvents, the original amide was obtained, showing that the reaction product, if at all formed, was decomposed during subsequent treatment.

It is well known that acetoacetic ester and its derivatives are in general more reactive than malonic ester and its corresponding derivatives, and therefore, it was thought advisable to modify the experimental conditions allowing a lower temperature for the reaction than that used by Naik and Jadhav. Pure dry benzene was selected as the solvent in the present work as it does not react with sulphur dichloride. The course of the reaction can be expressed as

The compound was precipitated very slowly, the precipitation appearing to be complete on the following day, though in some cases, the reaction mixture had to be kept for two days. To avoid the formation of a paste all precautions to exclude moisture had to be taken and the excess of sulphur dichloride was removed by several washings with dry benzene and dry petroleum.

The following considerations led us to assign the constitution given to these compounds.

(i) When the sulphide of acetoacet- β -naphthylamide is hydrolysed with caustic potash, β -naphthylamine is obtained.

(ii) The reduction by alkaline hydrosulphide gives back the original amide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Interaction of Sulphur Dichloride with Acetoacetanilide.—The amide (3.6 g., 1 mol.) was suspended in dry benzene (25 c. c.) in a conical flask and sulphur dichloride (3 g., 1.1 mol.) was added. The flask was immediately corked tightly with a calcium chloride tube.

The reaction started vigorously and copious fumes of hydrochloric acid were evolved and the amide went into solution. The reaction subsided after a few minutes and then slow evolution of fumes continued. After 3 hours extremely slow precipitation began, which was completed on the next day. It was then filtered and washed free from the dichloride with dry benzene and petroleum when it separated as minute silky crystals, m.p. 196-97°. The compound is sparingly soluble in benzene and alcohol and insoluble in carbon disulphide and petroleum. (Found: N, 6.96; S, 15.76. $C_{10}H_9O_2NS$ requires N, 6.72; S, 15.47 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide Sulphide.—5 G. of the compound were added to a solution of caustic potash (3 g.) in a small quantity of water and the whole was refluxed for 2 hours. The mixture was then cooled and filtered and the precipitate was washed with cold water till the filtrate was free from alkali. The solid, on recrystallising from hot water, gave rosy crystals, m. p. 110° (mixed m. p. with β -naphthylamine).

The solid residue, obtained on evaporating the filtrate to dryness, was treated with hydrochloric acid when hydrogen sulphide was found to evolve.

Reduction of Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide Sulphide by means of Alkaline Hydrosulphide.—5 G. of the compound were put into 50 c. c. of alcohol and refluxed for about an hour. An aqueous solution of sodium hydrosulphide (prepared by saturating 1.5 g. of caustic soda with hydrogen sulphide in a small quantity of water), and caustic soda (5.7 g. in a small quantity of water) was gradually added to it. The brown solution on dilution gave a precipitate,

which was filtered and washed free from alkali and crystallised from benzene and petroleum, m. p. 103°. It was thus found to be the original amide.

The other compounds were prepared in the same way and the following table summarises the properties of the compounds obtained from the amides.

Amides.	M.p.	Properties.	Formulae.	Analysis.	
				Found.	Calc.
Acetoacetanilide	196°	Silky needles	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NS	S, 15.76 N, 6.96	15.47 6.72
Acetoacet- <i>o</i> -toluidide	184°	Tuft-like crystals	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	S, 14.57 N, 6.57	14.48 6.34
Acetoacet- <i>p</i> -toluidide	130°	...	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	S, 14.79	14.48
Acetoacet- α -naphthylamide	184°	Needle-shaped crystals	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	12.70	12.45
Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide	179°	Soft small needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	12.74	12.45
Acetoacetylidide (r :4 :5)	209°	Amorphous	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	13.94	13.61
Acetoacetylidide (r :3 :4)	201°	...	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	14.06	13.61

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